

ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

The role and importance of education in the modern world are primary. Education and social development are closely related. For that reason, it is necessary to examine the theory of education and inequality. Social problems, material instability, and increasing class differences determine the future of an individual, both in social life and in education. Education is the essential parameter of assimilating social life as well as the bond between education with globalization and information technologies. Major changes had occurred in society due to the emergence of globalization and the development of information technologies. Globalization has a significant impact on the formal model of education of countries in transition, such as Serbia. Information technologies have become an important part of existence. Questions are being raised: is it necessary to introduce computers into schools and replace them with books? How does the use of modern technologies affect the mindset of the user?

Key words: Education, inequality, globalization, information technology, social development

Introduction

Education is the basic postulate of the contemporary society of every individual. The primary purpose of education is to teach an individual to take on a specific role in the community and to contribute to meeting basic needs. For centuries, education was a privilege for a small group of people. Books were multiplied manually until Gutenberg's printing press appeared in 1454. Educational progress arises with the emergence of industrialization. The spread of cities and migration from village to town results in the need for education, changing the education system.

In an industrialized world, literacy is rising rapidly, leading to an expansion of education.

Progress in the industrial economy has demanded a specialized and educated workforce. However, it's not the end of changes in society. The most significant achievement of the scientific and post-industrial society is information technology, which is claimed to be the third revolution - an informatics revolution.

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From an individual is expected to continually improve and educate, because IT education becomes a crucial factor. Regardless of what activity they were dealing with, informatics, called today digital literacy is of particular importance (faster and easier communication, online shopping, bank payment service, etc.). The emergence of modern technologies has also caused new social relations among the population. Social networks have enabled a new form of communication and, as such, they have reached the very top of popularity.

However, a new form of virtual communication and the possibility of modern technologies have enabled a new wave of problems, especially in the absence of sufficient IT knowledge or equipment. The lack of these two facts conditions the feeling of isolation from social life.

The modern education system is unimaginable without information technologies, and their presence is polarized from significant advantages to major shortcomings that will be discussed in this paper. Acquiring new knowledge and skills are the main tasks of education. However, we should not ignore the idea of humanism and socialization in order to establish ethical and cultural values.

Information technologies and education

There is no doubt that globalization is a major cause of advances in information technology. All these changes that have affected modern society from technological progress, the way of life, production systems to leisure time are conditioned by globalization. "If these processes are factors of a deep transformation of the world, globalization is the factor of its homogenization". [1] Globalization⁴⁷ is the term, which is used today, much more in a negative than positive context.⁴⁸ This term is used in media, political discussions, sociology, economics, etc. The important thing for globalization is: "to refer to the fact that we are living, more and more, in "one world" so that individuals, groups, and nations are becoming increasingly addictive" [3]. Globalization is the main cause of the development and rise of information and communication technologies. Today, information technologies have a huge impact on changes in contemporary society and are present in almost all areas of human creativity. "These changes are fast and distinctive everywhere - in the process of creating material goods and services, education and science, cultural and artistic creativity, in social communication and everyday life of people". [4]

The impact of information technology on education usually arises from the influence of information technologies on changes in contemporary society. As technologies are related to education, education is also related to technologies, especially in post-industrial societies. The progress of information technologies in many different ways influences education in schools. This means that education today does not end with

⁴⁷ Joseph Stiglitz in his work *Globalization and Its Discrepancy*, says: "Globalization is neither good nor bad. It has the power to bring enormous benefit, and for the countries of East Asia, which have accepted globalization under its own conditions and on its own dynamics, it was a huge benefit, despite the downturn during the 1997 crisis. But in a big part of the world, it did not bring similar benefits. For many, this seemed closer to the disaster without expertise" [2].

⁴⁸ Today, both at the far left and at the far right political parties, there is an anti-globalist attitude.

the acquisition of diplomas, certificates, and employment. Simply, the advancement of information technologies is conditioned by constant education and it is expected that the modern man learns throughout his whole life. That means that an individual is expected to be prepared for frequent workplace changes, a change of profession and the overcoming of new technological processes. [5] As Giddens says in his work *Sociology*: "The knowledge economy requires a computer-educated workforce and it is becoming increasingly clear that education can and must play a decisive role in meeting that need". [3]

In his work *Sociology: Themes and Perspectives*, Haralambos points out: "Workers must be flexible enough to introduce changes in the work they do in line with global competition and demand changes for certain goods and services. Companies and their workers must adapt to new opportunities and cannot rely on doing the same type of work throughout the entire working life". [6] We can say that the educational strategy that dominated the twentieth century, which concerned the specialization of certain types of occupations, was shaken. It should be replaced by a more modern educational strategy that would be adapted to high-speed technological changes. [5] Through an idea of society and a contemporary man who learns all life, information technologies impose an entirely new concept on education. Accordingly: "lifelong education and education as a development factor of a society correspond with the needs and goals of post-industrial society and such education are defined as postmodernist education". [4] Information technologies bring technological, social and psychological changes, as well as a diversified and effective approach to education. Information technologies change the access to traditional teaching, the way of acquiring knowledge, the quality of education and the educational environment, which leads to the fact that education must follow the trend of technological change and abandon the traditional form of teaching. [4]

However, the influence of information technology on educational changes does not appeal to everyone. John Ralston Saul, a Canadian writer and one of the leading intellectuals of today in his work *The Unconscious Civilization*, says: "Basic technical schooling is of course helpful. It should not, however, be treated as anything other than a way to shut down students into technology that will be outdated by the time they graduate. The time they lose will also deprive them of basic training in knowledge and thinking that could help them adapt to the constant changes that come from outside" [7]. Saul unambiguously points out that it is not necessary to rely entirely on technology, neglecting the basic idea and the purpose that education has: socialization and creation of critical thinking, which is important for every individual in social life.

In the following, Saul looked at the costs that schools must bear in order to acquire the latest equipment and latest programs and says: "An increasing number of schools spend a large part of their budget on computers and computer programs. Once they have enough equipment they will be able to sort out a full classroom of students behind machines where they will teach them in isolation something that has less intelligence than a man" [7]. Also, he points out that we will produce masses of students and pupils who will not be able to form their own opinion and who will rely on computers as "advanced and smart technology", which is not smarter than a human being, because without his instructions it cannot function.

Saul does not in any way attempt to impose our opinion by telling us whether the technology is needed and whether it can be of use to us. He only points out to us that this is just a machine and that depending on the direction we are given it can be harmful or useful.

Advantages and disadvantages of information technologies

The development of information technology has brought many innovations into our lives, with the emergence of new occupations everyday jobs are easier to perform. Today, the young population chooses professions related to the development of information technologies, and to work in the virtual world.⁴⁹ New generations have a completely different world view. Playing in parks, schoolyards, sports fields have replaced computers, tablets, mobile phones, and the Internet. Social networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Viber are very popular among youth, where they place their photos, expecting to get as many "likes" as it is a measurement unit of popularity. "There are countless values that this revolution carries, but we are not even aware of how many bad and potentially dangerous sides it can have" [8].

Life in the 21st century has become unimaginable without information technologies. The computer has become available to everyone, and children start using it from the earliest age. Of course, this has its advantages, but also its flaws. Today children spend more hours a day sitting for a computer playing video games and using the Internet. Someone might say that there is nothing wrong with that. However, sitting in front of a computer for several hours a day can have harmful effects on the health of the child, which should be spotted and prevented if it's possible. Experts often warn about these things concerning children's health:

- It affects the brain – Besides that of being a source of entertainment for kids from the fourth to the fifth year, the computer also represents a real "window" to the world. However, excessive use of the computer can cause unwanted consequences for the emotional and psychological development of the child, but also for his brain that is in the development phase.
- Disturbs physical activity – An hour spent on a computer is not a big problem, but if the child spends hours and hours in front of the screen, and this is his only form of entertainment, then it should be reacted because there is a fear of consequences for the child's development, first of all, muscles, eyes, joints and psyche.
- Eyesight problems – Eyes suffer the greatest consequences of excessive use of the computer, followed by a spine, back, neck and hands. The most common negative consequences are for child's eyesight, all due to multiple viewing in the monitor. To prevent this, you need to do next: the monitor should not be too close, the monitor should not have a glare, the letters on the screen must be large enough to see the child from a certain distance, and the air in the room must not be too dry.

⁴⁹ For example, work from home, the people who are dealing with this business, are calling a job of the future.

- Watch out on your Posture – Sitting in an irregular position creates a much greater problem for children than for adults because their bone and muscular structure are not sufficiently formed. As a result of the improper holding of the body, back pain is the most common problem that occurs.
- And the hands suffer – Since the child uses his hands while playing video games, pain usually occurs in the wrists of the hand due to the rapid movement of the mouse and keyboard.

Computers offer many numerous possibilities than television, and this is much more attractive today for the children than anything else. Besides all the faults we have listed, computers also have their own advantages, which children can use if they manage the computer correctly. The Internet is unquestionably the greatest advantage. The simplest example, we do not need to buy encyclopedias with the plant and animal world to show the child a particular plant or animal, because various images and sites with images of flora and fauna are available on the Internet. Interesting information about history and geography are numerous, followed by the maps of the world, where we are one click away from the desired destination, etc. The possibilities of the Internet are immense, only proper use is required, as well as help and control of parents over the children who use it. [9]

Excessive use of computers is not only harmful to children, but also to adults. Health problems of different types are most commonly felt by people who spend too much time on the computer and do not pay attention to the instructions related to ergonomics.⁵⁰ Diseases caused by long-lasting work on a computer that the experts are warning most are: carpal tunnel syndrome, insomnia, dehydration, deformities caused by repetition of the movement, headache, diabetes, glaucoma, obesity, neck pain, and back pain. [10]

One of the innovations brought about by the development of information technologies is "online" learning or the so-called, distance learning, which enables scholars and students to follow classes in "classrooms without walls"⁵¹ from home or anywhere else at a given moment. Like every innovation, learning "online" or "classrooms without walls" has its advantages and disadvantages.

The benefits that "online" education offers are:

- Flexibility – This means that at a given moment we can be found anywhere and at the same time we are in a virtual classroom where we get the whole material we need, starting with books, colleagues and professors. Virtual classrooms are always open and there is no fixed time when we need to "log in", it depends on us, whether we are overnight or over the day because there are no weekends and holidays for virtual classrooms.
- Multimedia – One mouse click is enough to make content with a particular topic available to us. Libraries are no longer needed, as books today are available in electronic format.
- Adjustment needs – This means that, through various animations, videos and images, learning is adapted to different ages from different layers of society. When there is a disadvantage of persons with disabilities, for hearing impaired persons,

⁵⁰ Ergonomics is a science that deals with product design, best adapting them to the human body.

⁵¹ "Classroom without walls" is the term used by Anthony Giddens in his work Sociology (2007).

much more material is available (video and text) than, for example, people with visual impairment, where a good solution should be found with a little more effort, while for people with physical disabilities there is no problem in the form of building barriers.

- The disadvantages of "online" education can be:
- The necessity of great motivation – When we are communicating and learning online, in a virtual classroom, there may be a lack of motivation, because it all seems less real, so we can easily give up. In "classroom without walls" we do not have a teacher or mentor who will motivate us to learn, we just log in, log out and that's it.
- Isolation of an individual - We are alone in the room, park or yard, but we are in class, in a virtual classroom full of people. Each one individually logs in for the class when he suits him or at the appointed time. In front of us are just a keyboard and monitor, and we express our opinion by typing comments or "chatting" in the group. [11]

It is in the nature of man to be surrounded by people. There is a great danger that a person becomes a "lonely individual"⁵² due to the excessive use of information technology.

Inequality in education

Socio-economic and social inequality represents the biggest problem of countries that have passed or are experiencing transition, which includes Serbia. According to the data of the Statistical Office, the poverty risk rate in 2017 was 25.7%, while the risk of poverty or social exclusion rate was 36.7%. [13]

However, if we look at the research of the Statistical Office on the use of computers and the Internet in Serbia, we come to the following data. In 2018, 72.1% of households own a computer, while 72.9% own Internet access. 67.5% of users access the Internet through mobile devices, while 51.2% of users use ADSL connection. If we look at the income level, 87.8% of users with 600 or more Euros have an internet connection, while 80.6% of users pay 300-600 Euros, and finally 56.8% of users with incomes of up to 300 Euros. [14]

Based on these results, we see that the internet is mostly used by citizens with a salary of about 600 Euros, but also that the percentage of those who receive up to 300 Euros is quite high, which is surprising, if we take into account all monthly expenses.

In his work *Social Aspects of Education*, Bazić points out that inequality in education, both socio-economic and social, is best observed through: the impact of socio-economic and social factors on the development of information technologies in education and the influence of information technologies on changes in socio-economic and social relations. This means that the impact of information technologies can be seen in all spheres of social life: in the country, in the family, in

⁵² The term "lonely individual" is used by Ljubodrag Simonović in his work *The Last Revolution* where he says: "...preserving the bridge is a challenge that far outweighs individual human abilities, and man as a lonely individual feels helpless before the incipient cataclysm. The most important duty of the life-giving mind is to point to the existential significance of sociability and in that way contribute to the development of man's need for a man". [12]

the region, etc. Impoverished families do not have enough resources to buy computers for their children, which leads children from deprived families to have a subordinate status compared to children who have computers at home. The advantage of children who own computers at home is that they have some basis before they go to school, where they will only later upgrade their knowledge. As to countries and regions, areas that are not sufficiently developed, have major problems to create basic conditions for the introduction of information technologies in schools due to lack of financial resources, poor infrastructure and lack of funds for the purchase of computers and accessories. We have schools located in the developed regions, which are advantageous for better infrastructure and easier purchase of computers. [4] From all this comes the fact that will: "Rural communities and underdeveloped regions, due to many socio-economic factors and the lack of modern technologies, experts in the field of information technologies, and appropriate education, are increasingly on the margins of socio-economic development, because the tendency is that capital, information technologies, and quality educational institutions concentrate on developed areas and cities". [4]

Conclusion

Based on all of the above, we conclude that the development of information technologies is undoubtedly a globalist phenomenon and that today life without information technologies is unimaginable. However, we need to pay attention to the extent to which we use these technologies. If they are indispensable for the work we do, it is necessary to spend spare time without excessive use of a computer, tablet or mobile phone. In the 21st century, it is inconceivable to live without information technologies; we need them, whether we want to acknowledge it or not, but their use should be rationalized.

When it comes to children and young people, it is relevant strictly to control the time spent with the computer. One hour a day is enough for playing video games, for social networks, etc., because the rest of the time should be focused on their social activity. When the use of information technologies is concerned, parents need to be involved in the process of monitoring their children.

The main controversy is that information technology has its own advantages and disadvantages. It is up to us to take advantage of these technologies because we have to keep the step with time. However, we must also point out problems that may be caused by the excessive use of these technologies.

The purpose of this paper is not a critique of information technologies and their development, but a warning to what does not want any of us to happen, which is to undermine the idea of humanism. As Albert Einstein said: "It has become horrifying that our technology has exceeded our humanity".

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